

Synthesis, spectral and thermal studies of some Nb^V complexes of polydentate ligands derived from 4-aminoantipyrine

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Abstract : Several novel complexes of Nb^V have been synthesized with the Schiff base, HL¹ derived from salicylaldehyde and 4-aminoantipyrine and an azodye, HL² derived from β-naphthol and 4-aminoantipyrine. The molecular structure of ligands, HL¹ and HL² have been established by single crystal X-ray crystallography. The complexes were characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance, IR, ¹H NMR and FAB mass spectral studies. The complexes have the general formulae [Nb(L¹)XCl₃] and [Nb(HL²)XCl₄], where X = Cl, NCS or NO₃. The IR spectra of these complexes indicate that the ligand, HL¹ acts as a monoanionic tridentate chelating agent and the ligand, HL² found to behave in a neutral bidentate manner. The optimized geometry of two complexes [Nb(L¹)Cl₄] (1) and [Nb(HL²)Cl₅] (4) have been obtained by molecular mechanics method.

Keywords : Niobium(v), 4-aminoantipyrine, ¹H NMR, thermal studies, 3D modeling.

Introduction

The complexes of niobium(v) with a wide range of Schiff bases containing a variety of donor sites have been reported in the literature^{1,2}. Niobium ions form complex species with virtually all types of neutral and anionic donors^{3,4}. Schiff bases of bioactive 4-aminoantipyrine and its complexes are known for their variety of applications in biological, clinical, pharmacological and analytical fields and also in the area of catalysis⁵. A survey of literature shows that very few Nb^V complexes of azodyes derived from biologically active molecule 4-aminoantipyrine have been reported.

Here, we report the synthesis, spectral and physico-chemical characterization, and thermal studies of complexes of niobium(v) species with a Schiff base (HL¹), derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and salicylaldehyde and an azo dye (HL²), naphtholazoantipyrine.

Results and discussion

All complexes are coloured, non-hygroscopic solids and stable in air. They are soluble in common organic solvents, like acetone, chloroform, methanol, acetonitrile, DMF and DMSO. The analytical and spectral data (Tables 1 and 2) show that all the complexes are mononuclear

with the general formulae [Nb(L¹)Cl₃X] and [Nb(HL²)Cl₄X], where X = Cl, NCS, NO₃. Molar conductivity data in 10⁻³ (M) methanol show that all the complexes are non-electrolytes⁶. All the niobium(v) complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected of a d⁰ system.

Molecular structure of HL¹ and HL² from single crystal X-ray data :

HL¹ and HL² crystallizes in the monoclinic space group P21/n and P21/c respectively with four molecules per unit cell. The unit cell dimensions, *a* = 7.5924(4) Å, *b* = 7.4941(4) Å, *c* = 27.2368(15) Å, cell angles, α = 90°, β = 95.291(3)° and γ = 90° for HL¹ and *a* = 18.727(3) Å, *b* = 6.3996(9) Å, *c* = 14.706(2) Å, cell angles, α = 90°, β = 91.150(8)° and γ = 90° for HL². The azomethine bond, C(12)-N(1) distance of HL¹ is 1.2868(17) is in conformity with a formal C=N bond (1.28 Å) and the C(7)-O(2) bond distance of 1.2292(16) Å is very close to formal C=O bond length^{7,8} of 1.21 Å. The C(7)-O(2) bond distance of HL² is 1.224(2) Å is also very close to formal C=O bond length. An ORTEP diagram of the ligands HL¹ and HL² along with the atom labelling are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively.

Infraed spectra :

The IR spectra of the complexes are very complicated

Table 1. Analytical data of ligand and complexes

Ligand/Complex	Found (Calcd.) (%)					
	C	H	N	Cl	S	M
HL ¹	70.42 (70.34)	5.59 (5.57)	13.65 (13.67)	–	–	–
HL ²	70.39 (70.37)	5.07 (5.06)	15.60 (15.63)	–	–	–
[NbCl ₄ (L ¹)] (1)	40.02 (39.95)	2.96 (2.98)	7.85 (7.76)	26.62 (26.21)	–	17.74 (17.17)
[NbCl ₃ NCS(L ¹)] (2)	40.64 (40.48)	2.92 (2.86)	9.97 (9.93)	18.95 (18.86)	5.74 (5.68)	16.62 (16.48)
[NbCl ₃ NO ₃ (L ¹)] (3)	38.04 (38.08)	2.86 (2.84)	9.91 (9.87)	18.87 (18.73)	–	16.41 (16.36)
[NbCl ₅ (HL ²)] (4)	40.24 (40.12)	2.96 (2.88)	8.63 (8.91)	27.92 (28.20)	–	14.91 (14.77)
[NbCl ₄ NCS(HL ²)] (5)	40.48 (40.57)	2.82 (2.78)	10.47 (10.75)	21.34 (21.77)	4.98 (4.92)	14.52 (14.26)
[NbCl ₄ NO ₃ (HL ²)] (6)	38.12 (38.50)	2.74 (2.76)	10.81 (10.69)	21.68 (21.64)	–	14.13 (14.18)

Table 2. Important IR spectral bands (cm⁻¹) of ligand and complexes

Ligand/ Complex	v(OH)	v(O–H)	v(C=O)	v(C=N)	v(N=N)
	free	hydrogen bonded	pyrazolone		
HL ¹	–	3061	1645	1593	–
HL ²	–	3059	1666	–	1468
[NbCl ₄ (L ¹)] (1)	–	–	1600	1543	–
[NbCl ₃ NCS(L ¹)] (2)	–	–	1602	1550	–
[NbCl ₃ NO ₃ (L ¹)] (3)	–	–	1604	1557	–
[NbCl ₅ (HL ²)] (4)	3433	–	1603	–	1444
[NbCl ₄ NCS(HL ²)] (5)	3417	–	1616	–	1440
[NbCl ₄ NO ₃ (HL ²)] (6)	3380	–	1612	–	1442

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of HL¹.

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram of HL².

with extensive vibrational coupling and overlapping of absorption bands. Important infrared spectral bands of the ligands and complexes and their tentative assignments are given in Table 2. The spectrum of the ligand HL¹ exhibits a broad medium band at 3061 cm⁻¹ is assigned to hydrogen bonded OH group. This band is absent in the spectra of all the complexes. This may be due to the deprotonation of phenolic OH on coordination with the metal ion⁹. In the complexes, HL¹ coordinates through carbonyl oxygen, azomethine nitrogen as evidenced by the shift of $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ to lower frequencies^{10,11}.

The spectrum of the ligand HL² exhibits a broad medium band at 3059 cm⁻¹ is assigned to hydrogen bonded OR group^{12,13}. In the spectra of the complexes, a new broad band appears ~3440 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of free -OH group and hence its non participation in coordination with the metal ion¹⁴. In the complexes the ligand HL² coordinates through carbonyl oxygen, one of the azo nitrogens as evidenced by the shift of $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{N=N}$ to lower frequencies^{15,16}. Thus the ligand exhibit a neutral bidentate behaviour in all the complexes, coordinating through the C=O and -N=N- groups only.

New weak bands at ~530 cm⁻¹ and at ~420 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes have been assigned to ν_{Nb-O} and ν_{Nb-N} modes respectively¹⁷. The N-coordinated nature of

the thiocyanate group is indicated by the bands at ~2060 cm⁻¹ (ν_{C-N}), ~850 cm⁻¹ (ν_{C-S}) and ~80 cm⁻¹ $\delta_{(NCS)}$. The IR spectra of the nitrate complexes suggest mono coordination of the nitrate group¹⁸ (ν_4 at ~1470 cm⁻¹, ν_1 at ~1350 cm⁻¹ and ν_2 at ~1034 cm⁻¹).

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra of HL¹ and the complex **1** were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the free ligand HL¹ showed a sharp signal at δ /ppm 12.953 characteristic of the phenolic OH proton which is absent in its complexes, suggesting coordination through deprotonated phenolic oxygen. The signal at δ 9.703 ppm of the ligand has shifted to δ 9.924 ppm indicating coordination of azomethine nitrogen in the complexes. It is due to the reduction of electron density at the azomethine C-H. Signals at δ 2.412 ppm (3H, s, C-CH₃), δ 3.216 ppm (3H, s, N-CH₃), 6.902–6.941 (3H, m, Ar), δ 7.298–7.571 ppm (5H, m, Ar phenyl) appears in the spectrum of ligand but on complexation, signals are shifted slightly to downfield¹⁹.

The ¹H NMR spectrum²⁰ of the free ligand HL² showed a sharp signal at δ 14.165 ppm characteristic of the phenolic OH proton. The spectrum displays two singlets, which correspond to methyl protons. The >C-CH₃ group of pyrazolone ring appears as a sharp singlet in the re-

gion δ 2.773 ppm while the $>N-CH_3$ signal is observed as another singlet in the region δ 3.431 ppm. The signal due to five aromatic protons of the antipyrine phenyl ring and these due to the protons of phenyl rings are observed as multiplet between δ 7.072–7.908 ppm. On analyzing the spectrum of $[Nb(HL^2)Cl_5]$, the presence of singlet due to phenolic proton indicates the non participation of the -OH group during coordination, which is further confirmed by the IR spectra.

Mass spectrometry :

The FAB mass spectra of complexes **1** and **4** were recorded and their stoichiometric compositions were compared. The complexes **1** and **4** show molecular ion peaks at m/z 540.16 and 627.58 respectively, suggesting the complexes to be monomeric. Presence of peaks at m/z 469.68 $[M-Cl-Cl]^+$, 433.65 $[M-Cl-Cl-Cl]^+$ and 398.16 $[M-Cl-Cl-Cl-Cl]^+$ in the mass spectrum of complex **1** suggests the presence of four chlorine atoms in the complex^{21,22}. These results are consistent with the proposed molecular composition of the complexes.

Thermal studies :

Thermal behavior of the complexes **1** and **4** were studied by TGA and DTG techniques by heating in air at a rate of 10 °C per min.

The decomposition of the complex **1** takes place in three stages as indicated by the DTG peaks at 228 °C and 544 °C. The stability range extended from ambient temperature to 180 °C. First decomposition stage starts at 180 °C and ended at 270 °C. The mass loss of 26.03% (Calcd. 26.21%) corresponded to the loss of anionic part of the complex. The second stage decomposition ranged from 520 °C to 570 °C. The weight loss in this stage was 24.49% (Calcd. 24.67%) ascribed to the oxidative decomposition of the remaining part of the complex to give Nb_2O_5 as the ultimate residue²³.

The thermal decomposition of the complex **4** occurred in two stages as denoted by the DTG peaks at 202 and 573 °C. The complex is stable upto 170 °C. The first stage decomposition starts at 170 °C and is completed at 230 °C. The mass loss of 27.56% (Calcd. 28.21%) corresponds to the elimination of five chlorine atoms²⁴. The second stage decomposition ranges from 530 to 610 °C. At the end of the second stage the ligand and anionic parts are completely removed and a residue approximating to Nb_2O_5 is formed. The mass loss from TG is 29.83% (Calcd. 29.51%).

3D molecular modeling :

The molecular model was constructed using Modeling and Analysis software ²⁵CHEM Bio3D Ultra 11.0. The possible 3D structures of **1** and **4** were optimized by molecular mechanics calculations, MM₂ giving the lowest energy CHEM 3D models^{26,27}. 3D structures of complexes **1** and **4** are given in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. Energy optimized configuration of $[NbCl_4(L^1)]$.

Fig. 4. Energy optimized configuration of $[NbCl_5(HL^2)]$.

On the basis of all the above spectral data and physico-chemical studies, a coordination number seven (Figs. 5 and 6) was suggested for the examined Nb^V complexes.

Fig. 5. Proposed structure of [NbCl₃X(L¹)].

Fig. 6. Proposed structure of [NbCl₄X(HL²)].

Experimental

Materials :

Niobium(V) chloride was from Fluka and all other chemicals were of AR grade.

Physical measurements :

Metal and chloride were estimated by standard methods²⁸. The elemental analyses (C, H, N and S) were carried out on a Vario EL-III CHN Elemental Analyser at the SAIF, Cochin University of Science and Technology, Kochi. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer using KBr pellets in the region 4000–400 cm⁻¹. The molar conductance of the complexes in methanol solutions (10⁻³ M) at room temperature were measured using a Elico direct reading conductivity meter. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz FT NMR instrument using TMS as reference. The

FAB mass spectrum of ligand HL¹, HL², [Nb(L¹)Cl₄] and [Nb(HL²)Cl₃] were recorded in a JEOL JMS600H mass spectrometer at NIIST, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India. Thermal analysis of the complexes [Nb(L¹)Cl₄] and [Nb(HL²)Cl₃] were carried out by heating in air at a rate of 10 °C per minute on a Mettler TG-50 thermo balance. Intensity data and cell parameters were recorded at room temperature (293 K) on a Bruker kappa apex II single crystal X-ray diffractometer equipped with graphite monochromated Mo Kα (λ = 0.71073 Å) radiation. The data integration and reduction were processed with SAINT software. Single crystal of HL¹ and HL² suitable for X-ray diffraction studies was grown from its methanol solutions by slow evaporation at room temperature in air. Structural refinement was carried out by full matrix least squares on F² (SHELXL-97) programme package²⁹. Molecular graphics employed includes ORTEP³⁰ and Mercury³¹. Full crystallographic data (cif file) relating to the crystal structure have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre as CCDC 892842 and 892843.

Synthesis of ligands :

The Schiff base, HL¹ (C₁₈H₁₇N₃O₂) was prepared by mixing methanolic solutions of salicylaldehyde (0.05 mol, 50 mL) and 4-aminoantipyrene (0.05 mol, 50 mL) and refluxed the mixture for 2 h. The pale yellow solid, separated on concentration, was filtered, washed with methanol and dried. Synthesis of ligand, HL² was carried out by 4-aminoantipyrene and β-naphthol as the case may be by diazotization and coupling as reported earlier³². Purity of the ligands were monitored by TLC. The IR, ¹H NMR, mass spectra and single crystal X-ray diffraction data of the ligands are discussed along with the complexes.

All the operations are carried out under nitrogen atmosphere. The chloride complex was prepared by NbCl₅ in chloroform (2 mmol, 20 mL) was added in small quantities with stirring to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol, 20 mL). The solution formed was refluxed for ~3 h. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with chloroform and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

The following general method was adopted for the preparation of thiocyanate and nitrate complexes. NbCl₅ in chloroform (2 mmol, 20 mL) containing 2 mmol of

NH₄CNS/2 mmol LiNO₃ as the case may be, was added to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol, 20 mL). The thiocyanate complex was precipitated on heating the mixture at 40 °C for ~30 min, while the nitrate complex was precipitated on refluxing the solution for ~2–3 h. The precipitated complexes were suction filtered, washed with chloroform followed by dry ether and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

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